

HR CHALLENGES IN SERVICE INDUSTRIES-A STUDY IN DIFFERENT ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract—Gone are those days when we used to talk about countries and economies on the basis of their major producing or production like Agriculture, Manufacturing, Technological, Financial, Oil, Knowledge(Educational) or Tourism and so on. But now the only sector or factor which is common to all of these industries are Services. So in this new millineal and fast digitizing world every country is rushing or trying to become a “ SERVICE-O-ECONOMY”. As services are growing at an unexpected rate and whatever the primary/main industry may be they have and are associated with or attached with their Services. Hence every country is into “SERVICEOCONOMY”. So to maintain a high and steady balanced growth rate of their economies the main challenge’s is to provide and maintain a good and Quality Service . These challenges are pronounced on the HR people and also on the “Servicepreneures “ respectively.

Keywords: Services, “Service-o-economy”, Servicepreneures.

Introduction

A service is any act or performance that one party can offer to another that is essentially intangible and does not result in the ownership of anything . Its production may or may not be tied to a physical product.Philip Kotler. [1]

As services are intangible and also Service quality is difficult to be rated. Also Service main challenge would be the factor Time and Convenience. Also the Service Personnel are 24x7

The major challenges for the HR people are

- 1) Compromising with the appointment process. i.e;
 - a) Management is not ready to offer salary compared to industry or competitive salary enough to survive and other benefits time to time say for the employee.
 - b) And also as skilled people are not available HR people take less skilled people since they have to show to the management the numbers. If available the management is not ready to pay the salary wanted by the employee.

c) And also another strong reason is that the HR people and the department trying to project themselves as a more profitable and accountable and successful than other departments in the organization.

Objective’s/Aim:

1. To study the HR challenges in respect with Service Industries.
2. Also to study the challenges of Servicepreneures

Research Methodology

The study is mainly based on secondary data. The secondary data is collected through books,journals and internet websites.

Review of Literature:

According to Lee Iwan Watkins top ten reasons for poor customer service are

1. **People are not trained.** When an organization does not spend the time to fully train their people the consequence is poor service.
2. **People don’t care.** Selecting the correct personality is crucial for your business success. Apathetic or self centered personality types have no place in a business that requires customer contact.
3. **Sabotage.** Angry or frustrated employees can actively work to sabotage and try to destroy the company.
4. **Employees don’t believe in the company, product or service.** If the image, marketing and promotion of the company is quite different from the reality, workers will not be able to sustain a positive attitude in the face of problems they know exist.
5. **Personal problems** reflected in work. When an employee’s personal life is in crisis or out of control, they may exercise control, aggression and negativism toward customers in an attempt to put some part of their life in order.

6. **Burnt out.** Too much negative, too many complaints can lower a person's level of commitment and move their positive and helpful attitude to an apathetic one.

7. **Not providing the correct solutions to customers, lack of empowerment.** There is nothing worse than dealing with an employee who listens to a problem, then shrugs and says they have to ask someone else in the company to intervene and provide a solution.

8. **Don't see the benefits – don't understand their role in the company.**

9. **Apathetic from hearing the same problems over and over.** A fundamental role of the customer service division is to provide constant feedback on how customers view the company, the products and the service. If this feedback is not analyzed and acted upon by upper management a feeling of apathy and frustration is created.

10. **Incentives/salary not tied to results.**

Practical HR Department and Management attitude effecting services

a) Apart from the Challenges the HR dept not giving in right advices to the Management when required.

b). Managements early resolve will not last long in the long run and they don't practice what they preach.

c).Management buys costly equipment but compromise on Training & Maintenance for the equipment. (Transport Companies buy Volvo vehicles at the cost of 4 crore rupees but not willing to pay enough salary to the drivers and Mechanics who maintain the buses).

Services of Industries effected

Airlines Industries : This is the Industry which is a classic example of all the above challenges given the Pilot's are overburden with flying and the Mangalore Tragedy where 300 lives were lost due to pilot s overworking and his dozing and snoring on the pilot seat where clearly audible in the recovered blackbox.

The less trained cabin staff and crew of the private airlines lack empathy and are least bothered about service and customer care . Of late we have about 12(dozen incidents) about not properly treating of customers especially by Indigo staff.

Mobile Industry: The Chinese mobile companies are more interested in profits and numbers rather than quality equipment . Most of the Chinese mobiles are blasting in mischarging of their batteries and due to faulty equipment.

Manufacturing (Cars) : Many of the multi-national companies and national companies of Car manufacturing make many faulty gears or air-bags not opening . Toyota and Volvo have recommended back some of their versions back to the manufacturing base

Health Care: Hospitals are becoming money minting machines for the Management as the doctors are fleecing the patients with recommending plenty of tests and costly surgical process for the patients even though they are not required. Max Care in New Delhi recently pronounced a new born baby as dead even though the baby was alive.

So definitely there will be mismatch with Industry Skills and Employability Skills

Findings :

It is now clearly known that HR people 's challenges are mainly associated with the Management and it is the whole and sole responsibility whether they wish to stay with their vision ,mission and statement or just for profiteering somehow and continue in the business. Also HR dept and people should be ethical before they try to earn profits or goals of the organization.

Conclusions

There is plenty of scope for further studies as we already said the next generation will be of Services, Services, Services and Services. Until one does not put interest in their employees definitely any organization cannot live up to their standards and performance and give excellent service.

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